

Synthesis of Ni(II), Co(II), Cu(II) Mixed-ligand Complexes Containing Amino Acid (Cysteine) and 1,10-phenanthroline

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Abstract:

A new three mixed-ligand complexes of some transition metal ions Co(II), Ni(II), Cu(II) with Cysteine (Cys) as a primary Ligand and 1,10-phenanthroline (phen) as a secondary ligands have been prepared by the formulas $[M(Cys)_2(phen)]$, $M = Co(II), Ni(II), Cu(II)$, $Cys = (C_3H_7NO_2S), (C_{12}H_8N_2) = (phen)$.

All the prepared complexes have been described by The UV-Visible Spectroscopy and Magnetic measurements (mimetic study) and the molar conductance values reveal that the all complexes are non-electrolytes since the complexes assume octahedral geometry in which the Co(II), Ni(II), Cu(II) have two molecules of Cysteine and one molecule from 1,10-phenanthroline in the coordination sphere.

Keywords: *mimetic study, molar conductance values, coordinate covalent bonds, ligand.*

Introduction

The bonds typically are divided according to however covalent or ionic in property. The third class is coordinate covalent bonds. In the last type of bond a molecule or atom have lone pair of electron (Lewis base) which is donated to unoccupied orbital on another metal/ion (Lewis acid) to form the new bond (Dreper, 2003). coordinate covalent bonds is formed due to lone pair of electrons come from molecule or atom, thus depend on electrostatic

attraction effect between lone pair of electrons and cation to form this type of bond. while participate as in typical covalent bond (Nugent, & Mayer, 1988). Well-known example is shown in Figure 1.

Thus viewed the lone pair of electrons on ligand (NH_3) are donated to an empty d-orbital on cobalt cation to form the $[Co(NH_3)_6]^{3+}$ complex ion.

Figure 1. Complex of Ammonia-Cobalt (III) Formed Coordinate Covalent Bond

In the above complex showed that neutral molecule or anion atom were bound directly to the metal so that complex salt such as $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_6]^{3+}$. Also demonstrated (Werner in 1913) that there were profound stereochemical consequence of the assumption that the molecules or ion (ligand) around the metal occupied position at the corners of the octahedron or square (Cotton, et al., 1988).

Now we can define a ligand as any molecule or ion that has at least one electron pair that can be so donate. Ligand may also be called Lewis base in term used inorganic chemistry, they are nucleophile. Metal ions or molecules such as BF_3 with incomplete valence electrons are Lewis acid or electrophile (Raj, 2008).

Coordination Number and Oxidation Number

Coordination number (secondary valence) is the number of ligands in a coordination complex that are attached to the metal centre. Therefore, we sometimes call it as ligancy. These ligands can be atoms, ions or molecules. Usually, we can observe coordination numbers from 2 to 9 in coordination compounds, but higher coordination numbers are very rare. However, this number does not involve the number of electron pairs around the metal centre. For, example, $[\text{Mo}(\text{CN})_8]^{4-}$ is a coordination complex having Molybdenum as the metal centre and the coordination number is 8 because there are eight ligands attached to the metal centre (Crabtree, 2009).

The oxidation number (primary valence) is the charge the central atom would have if all ligands and electron pairs shared with the atom were removed. Moreover, this number is for transition metals because the coordination complexes form via binding ligands with transition metals. Transition metals are the chemical elements in group 3 to 12 in d block of the periodic table. Typically, they can form several oxidation states due to the low reactivity of unpaired d electrons. For example, the oxidation number of iron (Fe) in the coordination complex $[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6]^{3-}$ is +3. We can obtain this value by removing all the ligands (CN ligands) with their charge (Durrant, & Durrant, 1970).

Overall charge is -3

Remove -1×6 (because there are six ligands and a Cn ligand has -1 charge)

Then, oxidation number of Fe = $-3 - (-6) = +3$

Figure 2. Show the Difference Between Primary, Secondary Valence and Counter Ion in Coordination Compound

Ligands

Ligands are the groups that form the coordination sphere. These groups form coordinate covalent bonds with the central metal Based on number of donor atoms. This ligand has electrons that are donated to the d- orbitals on the metal to form new coordinate covalent bonds, Ligands can be classified as follows:

- Monodentate Ligands: Also called as Unidentate Ligands. Only one atom donates

electrons for forming coordinate bond for example Cl^- , Br^- , NH_3 , H_2O (Palais, et al., 2008).

- Polydentate Ligands: Also called as multidentate Ligands. Two or more atoms donate electrons for forming coordinate bonds. The structures of these Ligands look like "crab" or "chelates", thus they are also called as chelating ligands e.g. Ethylene Diamine, EDTA – Ethylene Diamine Tetra Acetate.

Figure 3. Example for Polydentate Ligands

- Ambidentate Ligands: Two or more donor atoms are present, but while forming compound, only one atom forms coordinate bond with central metal (Aminou, et al., 2003).

This chapter includes chemicals, instrumentals, and procedures for the synthesis metal complexes and includes table that show physical properties and number of moles which are requirements for preparation of the complexes and lastly includes schematic representation preparation for these complexes.

Figure 4. Example for Ambidentate Ligands

Materials

Table 1. Solvents and Chemicals

Chemicals	Formula	M.wt(g/ mole)	%Purity	Company
Copper chloride dihydrated	$\text{CuCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$	170	98	B.D.H
Cobalt chloride hexahydrate	$\text{CoCl}_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$	237	99	B.D.H
Nickel chloride hexahydrate	$\text{NiCl}_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$	237	97	Laboratory rasayan
Sodium hydroxide	NaOH	40	98	B.D.H
Absolute ethanol	$\text{C}_2\text{H}_6\text{O}$	46	99.9	Hayman
Cysteine	$\text{C}_3\text{H}_7\text{NO}_2\text{S}$	121	98	B.D.H
1,10-Phenanthroline	$\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_8\text{N}_2$	180	98	B.D.H

Instrumentation

Melting points: Melting points for compounds

were measured by [Stuart melting point/ SMP30] apparatus.

Electric balance: The weights for compounds are measured by Sartorius apparatus which have four decimal places. Hot plate magnetic stirrer. For procedure, the reactions were using heated from type [lab tech- korea].

Conductivity measurements: The Conductivity for complexes was measured by [Digital conductivity meter-WT-720-inolab - Germany] in College of Science- Kerbala university.

Synthesis of Complexes

General Synthesis of the mixed-ligands metal complexes

A solution of cysteine (0.25g,2mmol) in 10ml of aqueous ethanol (1:1) containing (0.08g,2mmol)of sodium hydroxide and solution of 1,10-phenanthroline(0.18g,1mmol) in 10 ml of aqueous ethanol (1:1) were additional simultaneously to solution of $\text{CoCl}_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ or $\text{NiCl}_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ or $\text{CuCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (0.25g,1mmol) in 10ml of aqueous ethanol (1:1) the stoichiometric ratio [2Cys:1,10-phen:M]. The mixture was stirred and refluxed for 1.5-2h (Figure 5). The precipitate was filtered and washed with cold aqueous ethanol (1:1) several times and dried under oven and studied using standard method. Table 2 shows some physical properties and the number of moles complexes.

Table 2. Number of Moles for Phenanthroline and Cysteine, Metal Chloride and Some of Physical Properties of Prepared Complexes

compound	M.wt g/mol	Moles of phen	Moles of Cys	Moles of salt	Yield%	Color	Melting point °C
Phen = $\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_8\text{N}_2$	180	1	2	1	-	White	290
L-H= $\text{C}_3\text{H}_6\text{O}_2\text{N}_2$	121	1	2	1	-	White	240
[Co(phen)(cys) ₂]	476	1	2	1	85	Violet	324de
[Ni(phen)(cys) ₂]	480	1	2	1	80	Green	345de
[Cu(phen)(cys) ₂]	485	1	2	1	83	Blue	355de

Note: de=decomposition

Figure 5. Schematic Representation Preparation of the Complexes [M(Cys)₂(phen)]

The UV-Visible Spectroscopy and Magnetic measurements

The electronic spectra of the ligands and there complexes were recorded in DMF and their

assignments are given in Table 3. The free ligand 1,10-Phenanthroline spectral data display two bands at 311 nm (32154 cm⁻¹), 338 nm (29586 cm⁻¹) attributed to $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ and $n \rightarrow \pi^*$ transitions and the spectrum of the free ligand (L-valine), exhibits absorption peak at (280 nm)(35714 cm⁻¹) and an intense peak at 320 nm (31250 cm⁻¹), which assigned to ($\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$), and ($n \rightarrow \pi^*$) transition respectively (Fayad, Al-Noor, & Ghanim, 2012). In the Cu(II) complex is observed multiple absorption band at about 11210 cm⁻¹ –16510 cm⁻¹ but they are overlapped. Because, octahedral complexes of Cu(II) are observable distorted by Jahn-Teller effect. It was taken notice of top of the peak as absorption band and d-d transition at about 13010 cm⁻¹ (²E_g→²T_{2g}) for Cu(II) complex. The electronic spectrum of Ni(II)- complex exhibited

three bands in the region 10800, 16700 and 25670 cm⁻¹ corresponding to the transitions ³A_{2g}→³T_{2g}, ³A_{2g}→³T_{1g} and ⁴A_{2g}→³T_{1g} (P) respectively for octahedral geometry (Fayad, et al., 2013). The magnetic moment value of this complex was found 3.11 BM which was very close to the value of a distorted octahedral environment. The electronic spectra of Co(II)-complex displayed three bands at 10250, 15640 and 19670 cm⁻¹ corresponding to the transitions ⁴T_{1g}→⁴T_{2g}(F), ⁴T_{1g}→⁴A_{2g}(F), and ⁴T_{1g}→⁴T_{1g} (P) respectively (Fayad, et al., 2013). These transitions as well as the measured value of magnetic moment 4.82 BM suggested the octahedral geometry for this complex. The electronic spectral data along with the observed magnetic moment of Cu(II) (1.87 BM) complex suggested for a distorted octahedral geometry.

Table 3 Electronic Spectral Data, Magnetic Moment, of the Studied Complexes

Compound	λ max (nm)	ν (cm ⁻¹)	Assignments	μ_{eff} B.M
L- Val H	320	35714	$n \rightarrow \pi^*$	-
	280	31250	$\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$	
Phen (C ₁₂ H ₈ N ₂)	338	29586	$n \rightarrow \pi^*$	
	311	32154	$\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$	
Co[(phen)(Val) ₂]	975	12510	⁴ T _{1g} → ⁴ T _{2g}	4.82
	639	15640	⁴ T _{1g} → ⁴ A _{2g}	
	508	19670	⁴ T _{1g} → ⁴ T _{1g}	
Ni[(phen)(Val) ₂]	925	10800	³ A _{2g} → ³ T _{2g}	3.11
	598	16700	³ A _{2g} → ³ T _{1g}	
	389	25670	⁴ A _{2g} → ³ T _{1g} (P)	
Cu [(phen)(Val) ₂]	768	16638	² E _g → ² T _{2g}	1.87

Note: Val= (C₅H₁₁NO₂), (phen) = (C₁₂H₈N₂)

Conductivity

Conductivity for complexes is an important technique to study the nature of complexes. Conductivity of solution is based on number of charges in an ionic material and concentration solute. Ions migrate under the influence of the electric field if the solution of an electrolyte conducts. Hence, the capacity of any ion to transport charge depends on move of ions. Since by detect the solution conductivity one can determine the electrolytic or non-electrolytic nature of the metal complexes, which assist to achieve its ionic and covalent nature. The molar

conductivity (Λ) of solution of complex detect the number and rate of migration of cations and anions in one mole of complex. Finally, from the molarity of solution (M) and specific conductivity (K) the molar conductivity (Λ) was determined by the equation.

M molarity of solution

$$\Lambda = \frac{K \times 1000}{M} \quad (1)$$

The molar conductivity has unit S.cm². mol⁻¹ or ohm⁻¹ cm² mol⁻¹.

Table 4. Shows the Value of Molar Conductivity ($10^{-3}M$) for Different Types of Electrolytes in Different Solvents

Solvent	Non electrolyte	Types of electrolyte			
		3:3	3:2	3:1	3:4
Water	0	321	241	161	481
DMSO	0-20	71-41	70-90	90-120	120-240
DMF	0-30	65-90	130-170	200-240	111
ethanol	0-20	35-45	70-90	120	160

Source: Geary, 1971

According to the previous relation, the molar conductance(Λ) for complexes was calculated,

where C is the molar concentration of the metal complex, the results were shown in Table 5.

Table 5. Molar Conductivities of Prepared Complexes at Ethanol (as a Solvent) and Concentration ($10^{-3}M$) and T=298K

Sample of complex	Conductivity $\mu s/cm$
[Co(phen)(cys) ₂]	8
[Ni(phen)(cys) ₂]	11
[Cu(phen)(cys) ₂]	19

Table 6. Solubility of Mixed Ligand Metal Complexes

Sample of complex	EtOH	MeOH	Acetone	D.water	DMF	DMS
[Co(phen)(cys) ₂]	+	÷	-	+	+	+
[Ni(phen)(cys) ₂]	+	÷	-	+	+	+
[Cu(phen)(cys) ₂]	+	÷	-	+	+	+

Note: (+): Soluble; (-): Insoluble, (÷) Partially dissolve

The observed molar conductance of all the complexes in table 5 when compared with the values of molar conductivity are given in table 4. This suggests the non-electrolytic nature of these complexes (Temel, et al., 2003).

Solubility

Solubility of all the synthesized mixed- ligand metal complexes along with (Cysteine and ,10-phenanthroline) was checked by using different solvents. The synthesized complexes are soluble in DMF, DMSO, partially soluble in MeOH, soluble in EtOH, and insoluble in Acetone,. The solubility of all the synthesized complexes is represented in Table 6.

Proposed Structures of the Complexes

Figure 6. Structure of [Co(phen)(cys)₂] Complex

Figure 7. Structure of [Ni(phen)(cys)₂] Complex

Figure 8. Structure of [Cu(phen)(cys)₂] Complex

Application of Coordination Metal Complexes

The numeral of multidrug-resistant bacteria is wild becoming a universal interest (Saravanan, et al., 2011). Thus, the detection of new active compounds against new targets is a matter of earnestness. This instinct paying materials originating from wild growing material have shortened the life distance of the sources. This problematic has magnetized care of the scientific community in general to consider and explore transition metal complexes as alternative solutions for this difficult (Bruijninx, & Sadler, 2009). 1,10-phenanthroline Among the ligands are have the ability to tune on the chemical properties of metal ions. Also among other

beautiful properties 1,10-phenanthroline has a severe structure and possesses a excellent ability to chelate many metal ions via its two nitrogen centers. The resulting complexes show potential for numerous applications due to their high charge transfer mobility among other attractive properties. Also Phenanthroline metal complexes relatively ineffective against Gram-negative organisms otherwise can be bacteriocidal and bacteriostatic toward many Gram- positive bacteria This include stabilization of different oxidation states (Bruijninx, & Sadler, 2009) and modulation of the, electrophilic solvophilicity and nucleophilic properties of the metal. Copper is one of the metals acting as an essential trace element involved in antioxidant defense, cellular respiration, neurotransmission, cellular iron metabolism and connective tissue biosynthesis. Furthermore, several studies provide indication that copper ions are capable of interacting directly with nuclear proteins and DNA, producing site-specific damage (Saravanan, et al., 2011). In addition, it has been reported that copper compounds increase cell death in different cell cultures and delay cell-cycle progression. Cu (II) binds to DNA with high degree of affinity and thus promotes DNA oxidation. Copper (II) ions binding to specific sites can modify conformation of proteins, polynucleotides, or membranes (Shindo, & Brown, 1965). From this viewpoint copper (II) complexes have become the aims in addressing certain cancer problems. In this concern, complexes of copper containing 1, 10-phenanthroline (phen) as a ligand mixed with other types of ligands stimulated great benefits since they exhibit several biological activities such as anti-candida activity antitumor, antibacterail. Possibly the greatest widely studied cation in this respect is Cu²⁺, since a host of low molecular weight copper complexes have been confirmed beneficial against several diseases such as rheumatoid, gastric ulcers, tuberculosis, However Transition metal ions are playing an important role in biological methods in the human body. For example, nickel (II) and zinc (II) ions are the most abundant transition metals in humans. They are found either at the active sites or as structur components of a good

number of enzyme. Metal complexes containing nitrogen and sulphur donors have been proved to be component of several vitamins and drugs as well as potential antibacterial and fungal agents. The products resulting from the reaction of metal ion (in salt form) with amino acid in molar ratio of one mole of metal to one to three moles of amino acids to form a coordinate covalent bond. The average weight of hydrolyzed 5 amino acid must not be more than 150 Da and the molecular weight of the complex must not be exceed 800 Da". Amino acids in a complex provide the metal ion with an organic structure to shield its charge and facilitate its absorption. Elucidated the structure of these complexes Through conductometric experiments, the nature of the bond between amino acid and the metal ion was determine to be non- ionic in nature, later termed as coordinate covalent bond. Amino acids function as a good substrate due to the presence of both amino and carboxylate functional groups. They can form complexes with metal ions through electrostatic as well as co-ordinate covalent interaction. Different amino acids and metal ions have different extents of complexation. The stability constants of amino acid-metal ion complexes are lower than some synthetic ligands. For example, metal ions such as Ca^{2+} and Mg^{2+} form relatively weaker complexes than metals such as Fe^{3+} and Cu^{2+} . Amino acid complexes metal ions can be used as a better alternative for sugar-electrolyte solutions in

Long duration physical exercise. Complexes of transition metals with amino acids in proteins and peptides are utilized in numerous biological processes, such as electron transfer, oxygen conveyer and oxidation. In these procedures , the enzymatic active site, which is very specific, forms complexes with divalent metal ions (Soukup, & Schmid, 1985). And one of the complexes has been revealed to persuade apoptosis of murine leukemia cell lines With the resultant improved ability to infuse the cell membrane of the microbes, due to increased lipophilic character of these coordinated compounds, have been suggested as causes for their improved activity over their parent ligands. Supports this theory by Chelation, which has been described to decrease the polarity of the metal ion by partial sharing of its positive charge with the donor group of ligands. Carboxylate complexes have an extremely rich chemistry, owing mostly to numerous coordination modes showed by carboxylate groups. Unsaturated carboxylates use as ligands has increased extremely lately because their interesting biologic properties and structural architectures. Unsaturated carboxylates possess polymerisable groups, they become appropriate for biological applications(implantable medical devices, tissue engineering, dentistry, bone repair, etc.) due to their structures , low molecular weight, and architectures that may be modulated through controlled reactions (Rao, 1973).

Table 7. Example of Metal Complexes and Its Application

Complex	Potential
	<p>1. In analytical chemistry for determine elements such away Ni(II),Fe(II),Cu(II), etc (Geary, 1971)</p>

	<p>Against bacteria and yeast (Temel, et al., 2003)</p>
	<p>Anticancer, antifungal agent and antibacterial (Saravanan, et al., 2011)</p>

Conclusion

2- New three mixed Ligand complexes of some transition metal ions Co(II), Ni(II), Cu(II) with Cysteine (Cys) as a primary Ligand and 1,10-phenanthroline (phen) as a secondary ligands have been prepared with the formulas $[M(Cys)_2(phen)]$, $M = Co(II), Ni(II), Cu(II)$, $Cys = (C_3H_7NO_2S), (C_{12}H_8N_2) = (phen)$.

3- All the prepared complexes have been described by The UV-Visible Spectroscopy and Magnetic measurements (mimetic study)

4- The molar conductance values reveal that the all complexes are non-electrolytes since the complexes assume octahedral geometry in which the Co(II), Ni(II), Cu(II) have two molecules of Cysteine and one molecule from 1,10-phenanthroline in the coordination sphere.

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